

RESULTS OF CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF «SPRING NO 6» IN GALLAOROL
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Abstract: The article contains the results of chemical analysis of the water of the spring (Spring No. 6) located in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region. The spring water sample was examined by the analytical laboratory method, and the results of physical and chemical analysis of water, in particular, pH, SiO₂, dry residue, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe, CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl, NO₂, NO₃, total hardness, K, indicators such as Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al were determined. And coordinates of the location of Spring No. 6 were obtained. The results of the chemical analysis were compared with the state standards of Uzbekistan, and the spring water was found to be chemically suitable for domestic and drinking purposes.

Key words: Spring water, chemical analysis, Gallaorol district, state standards, human health.

Water constitutes about 75% of the Earth's surface [1]. A spring is a point of exit at which [groundwater](#) from an [aquifer](#) flows out on top of [Earth's crust \(pedosphere\)](#) and becomes [surface water](#). It is a component of the [hydrosphere](#). Springs have long been important for humans as a source of [fresh water](#), especially in [arid](#) regions which have relatively little annual rainfall [2]. Most of Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region includes mountainous areas. Gallaorol is a district in Jizzakh region. Gallaorol is located in the western, southwestern part of the region. It borders Farish to the north, Jizzakh to the east, Bakhmal districts to the south, Samarkand region to the southwest and west. The area is 2.0 thousand km². Coordination indicators of the district N: 39° 59'17,5"; E: 67° 35'2,4" [3]. Buloq No. 6 located in the village of Gumsoy, Gallaorol district. 6 (coordinates N: 39° 56'35.6"; E: 067°18'58.2") is one of the main sources of water for the residents of this village.

Below, the results of the chemical analysis of the sample taken from this spring water are presented and analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 6 is 7.8, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality

of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO_2 indicator of spring water is 1.2 mg/dm^3 , and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 310 mg/dm^3 , and the state standards state that it should be $1000.0\text{-}1500.00 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca^{2+} from cations is 56.1 mg/dm^3 , the amount of Mg^{2+} is 18.2 mg/dm^3 , Fe - $<0.05 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, and meets state standards. From anions, CO_3^{2-} - $<0.05 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, HCO_3^- - 176.9, SO_4^{2-} - 87.0, Cl - 7.09, NO_2 - 0.01, NO_3 - 0.8 mg/dm^3 , conforms to state standards. The dry residue of spring water is $4.3 \text{ mg-equiv/dm}^3$, which meets the standard requirements.

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 6 (Table 1).

Table 1.

Chemical analysis results of spring 6 (mg/dm^3)

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm^3	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm^3
1	K	4,5	7	Zn	0,03
2	Na	22,9	8	Ni	0,06
3	Mn	$<0,05$	9	Co	0,11
4	Pb	$<0,02$	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,01	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,03	12	Al	$<10,0$

Chemical analysis results (Table 1) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

References:

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- [3] <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki>